

HOW TO CURE VARICOSE VEINS WITH VNUS CLOSURE PROCEDURE?

Varicose veins are remarkably bothersome for several people, because not only are they ugly, but also because they generate pain and itching and so much uneasiness in our legs and ankles. Luckily there is a **varicose vein treatment South Shore** that truly works, so there is hope to get rid of them permanently.

Why do veins enlarge?

Veins are narrow-enclosed blood vessels that carry the blood throughout a person's body, from the tissues inside the body to the heart. Veins enlarge when a few of the valves amid the profound and surface veins in an individual's leg do not work adequately anymore leading to varicose veins. Such type of vein problem requires [vein treatment long island](#).

Two chief systems exist within a person's veins:

Deep (profound) veins:

These veins lie among each muscle and carry about ninety percent of the blood toward the heart

Superficial (surface) veins:

These veins are generally obvious and are just below the skin, whereas superficial veins are not guarded by the muscles like surface veins are. That means that the surface veins are not as powerful and there is more of a risk of varicose veins occurring. Consult a **vein specialist Jericho** to relieve these problematic veins.

Superficial veins carry blood via the skin and outer areas into the profound veins through joining passages (the perforator veins). To eliminate superficial veins or deep veins, get **vein treatment near me**.

When valves do not function adequately, blood can stream in the wrong direction since the force within the profound veins is larger than it is within the surface veins.

- Rather than obtaining blood from the surface or superficial veins, the deeper veins might essentially be forced back inside the superficial veins

- This instance causes an increase of force within the noticeable veins while blood assembles within the superficial veins and the force inside these veins rises, progressively, the valves start to fail
- As time goes on, possibly years later, each valve, one at a time, fails when this instance occurs, the superficial veins enlarge due to the additional blood and elevated pressure, which is how varicose veins occur

How to Relieve Varicose Veins Pain and Discomfort at Home:

- Overweight individuals should attempt to lose some weight.
- Support hose, similar to pantyhose, obtained via a pharmacy helps some folks.

A Modern and Effective Varicose Veins Treatment Alternative

VNUS Closure Procedure:

A slightly intrusive treatment to relieve varicose veins symptoms and enlargement of them. It involves lower amounts of pain and not as much bruising, especially when compared to alternative treatments such as modern vein-stripping surgical procedures. When people choose the closure method, [vein doctor](#)(s) shut the unhealthy veins by way of implanting a closure catheter, which goes within a vein and heats the walls of the vein by way of temperature-regulated RF power. When the vein is heated, the collagen (a natural body protein) within the vein's wall shrinks, and the veins close. As soon as the vein is sealed, blood starts flowing naturally and is rerouted to the healthier veins.

Venous deficiency (or venous reflux) occurs when each valve that normally keeps the blood streaming from the legs to the heart becomes damaged or weak.